

Distance functions of carabids in crop fields depend on functional traits, crop type and adjacent habitat: a synthesis

ESM 4: Post-processing and visualization of parameter estimates

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Summary

This appendix details the post-processing and visualization of model parameter estimates. Parameter estimates are marginalized using `emmeans` (Lenth 2021) and visualized using `ggplot2` (Wickham 2016) and `ggdist` (Kay 2021). We also present parameter *contrasts*, i.e. pairwise differences between parameters, such as the beta coefficients for different crops and habitats.

Prepare environment

Load packages

```
library(tidybayes)
library(ggdist)
library(patchwork)
library(brms)
library(emmeans)
library(flextable)
library(tidyverse)
```

Load data and models

```
##### Data files #####
meta_rich <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich.rds")
meta_rich_predatory <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_predatory2.rds")
meta_rich_granivorous <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_granivorous.rds")
meta_rich_omnivorous <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_omnivorous2.rds")
meta_rich_omnivorous_b <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_rich_omnivorous3.rds")
meta_abund <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund.rds")
meta_abund_diet <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_diet2.rds")
meta_abund_diet_b <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_diet3.rds")
meta_abund_size <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_abund_size.rds")
meta_CWM <- readRDS("../data/processed/meta_CWM2.rds")

##### Richness models #####
## Aggregate
brm_rich_00 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_00.rds")

## Predatory
brm_rich_11 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_11.rds")

## Omnivorous
brm_rich_12 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_12.rds")

## Omnivorous (without Poecilus cupreus)
brm_rich_12b <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_12b.rds")

## Granivorous
brm_rich_20 <- readRDS("../output/brm_rich_20.rds")

##### Activity density models #####
## Aggregate
brm_abund_00 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_00.rds")

## Predatory
brm_abund_11 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_11.rds")

## Omnivorous
brm_abund_12 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_12.rds")

## Omnivorous (without Poecilus cupreus)
brm_abund_12b <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_12b.rds")

## Granivorous
brm_abund_20 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_20.rds")

## Small
brm_abund_30 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_30.rds")

## Medium
brm_abund_40 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_40.rds")

## Large
```

```
brm_abund_50 <- readRDS("../output/brm_abund_50.rds")
```

Define custom functions

Posterior tabulation

```
slope_tab <- function(mod, trapDays = FALSE) {

  # Make this functional conditional on whether log.trap.days is included in the model
  if(trapDays == TRUE) {

    mod %>%
      # Spread draws from slope parameters
      spread_draws(b_distance100, `b_distance100:crop.poolVegetable`,
                   `b_distance100:crop.poolOilseed`, `b_distance100:crop.poolLegume`,
                   `b_distance100:crop.poolMaize`, `b_distance100:snh.typeherbaceous`,
                   `b_distance100:snh.typewoody`, b_log.trap.days) %>%
      # Back transform from log-odds to proportions
      mutate(Cereal = exp(b_distance100/10), # dividing by 10 puts us back on the 10 m scale
             # interaction slopes combine additively with the reference level slope
             Vegetable = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolVegetable`/10)),
             Oilseed = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolOilseed`/10)),
             Legume = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolLegume`/10)),
             Maize = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolMaize`/10)),
             control = exp(b_distance100/10),
             herbaceous = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:snh.typeherbaceous`/10)),
             woody = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:snh.typewoody`/10)),
             log.trap.days = exp(b_log.trap.days/10)) %>%
      select(.chain, .iteration, .draw, Cereal, Vegetable, Oilseed, Legume,
            Maize, control, woody, herbaceous, log.trap.days) %>%
      # Add contrasts
      mutate(crp.con.cereal_vegetable = Cereal - Vegetable,
             crp.con.cereal_oilseed = Cereal - Oilseed,
             crp.con.cereal_legume = Cereal - Legume,
             crp.con.cereal_maize = Cereal - Maize,
             crp.con.vegetable_oilseed = Vegetable - Oilseed,
             crp.con.vegetable_legume = Vegetable - Legume,
             crp.con.vegetable_maize = Vegetable - Maize,
             crp.con.oilseed_legume = Oilseed - Legume,
             crp.con.oilseed_maize = Oilseed - Maize,
             crp.con.legume_maize = Legume - Maize,
             sh.con.control_herbaceous = control - herbaceous,
             sh.con.control_woody = control - woody,
             sh.con.herbaceous_woody = herbaceous - woody) %>%
      pivot_longer(cols = -c(.chain, .iteration, .draw),
                   values_to = "coef", names_to = "par") %>%
      # Group parameters into classes
      mutate(class = case_when(
        par %in% c("Cereal", "Vegetable", "Oilseed", "Legume", "Maize") ~ "crop",
        par %in% c("control", "herbaceous", "woody") ~ "habitat",
        grepl("crp.con", par) ~ "crop.contrast",
        grepl("sh.con", par) ~ "habitat.contrast",
        grepl("trap", par) ~ "trapping.days",
      ))
  )
}

else{
  mod %>%
    # Spread draws from slope parameters
    spread_draws(b_distance100, `b_distance100:crop.poolVegetable`,
                 `b_distance100:crop.poolOilseed`, `b_distance100:crop.poolLegume`,
                 `b_distance100:crop.poolMaize`, `b_distance100:snh.typeherbaceous`,
                 `b_distance100:snh.typewoody`) %>%
    # Back transform from log-odds to proportions
    mutate(Cereal = exp(b_distance100/10),
           Vegetable = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolVegetable`/10)),
```

```

Oilseed = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolOilseed`/10)),
Legume = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolLegume`/10)),
Maize = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:crop.poolMaize`/10)),
control = exp(b_distance100/10),
herbaceous = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:snh.typeherbaceous`/10)),
woody = exp((b_distance100/10) + (`b_distance100:snh.typewoody`/10))) %>%
select(.chain, .iteration, .draw, Cereal, Vegetable, Oilseed, Legume,
Maize, control, woody, herbaceous) %>%
# Add contrasts
mutate(crp.con.cereal_vegetable = Cereal - Vegetable,
crp.con.cereal_oilseed = Cereal - Oilseed,
crp.con.cereal_legume = Cereal - Legume,
crp.con.cereal_maize = Cereal - Maize,
crp.con.vegetable_oilseed = Vegetable - Oilseed,
crp.con.vegetable_legume = Vegetable - Legume,
crp.con.vegetable_maize = Vegetable - Maize,
crp.con.oilseed_legume = Oilseed - Legume,
crp.con.oilseed_maize = Oilseed - Maize,
crp.con.legume_maize = Legume - Maize,
sh.con.control_herbaceous = control - herbaceous,
sh.con.control_woody = control - woody,
sh.con.herbaceous_woody = herbaceous - woody) %>%
pivot_longer(cols = -c(.chain, .iteration, .draw),
values_to = "coef", names_to = "par") %>%
# Group parameters into classes
mutate(class = case_when(
par %in% c("Cereal", "Vegetable", "Oilseed", "Legume", "Maize") ~ "crop",
par %in% c("control", "herbaceous", "woody") ~ "habitat",
grepl("crp.con", par) ~ "crop.contrast",
grepl("sh.con", par) ~ "habitat.contrast"
))
}
}

intercept_tab <- function(mod) {

mod %>%
# Spread draws from intercept parameters
spread_draws(b_Intercept, `b_crop.poolVegetable`,
`b_crop.poolOilseed`, `b_crop.poolLegume`,
`b_crop.poolMaize`, `b_snh.typeherbaceous`,
`b_snh.typewoody`) %>%
# Back transform to response scale
mutate(Cereal = exp(b_Intercept),
Vegetable = exp(`b_crop.poolVegetable` + b_Intercept),
Oilseed = exp(`b_crop.poolOilseed` + b_Intercept),
Legume = exp(`b_crop.poolLegume` + b_Intercept),
Maize = exp(`b_crop.poolMaize` + b_Intercept),
control = exp(b_Intercept),
herbaceous = exp(`b_snh.typeherbaceous` + b_Intercept),
woody = exp(`b_snh.typewoody` + b_Intercept)) %>%
select(.chain, .iteration, .draw, Cereal, Vegetable, Oilseed, Legume,
Maize, control, woody, herbaceous) %>%
# Add contrasts
mutate(crp.con.cereal_vegetable = Cereal - Vegetable,
crp.con.cereal_oilseed = Cereal - Oilseed,
crp.con.cereal_legume = Cereal - Legume,
crp.con.cereal_maize = Cereal - Maize,
crp.con.vegetable_oilseed = Vegetable - Oilseed,
crp.con.vegetable_legume = Vegetable - Legume,
crp.con.vegetable_maize = Vegetable - Maize,
crp.con.oilseed_legume = Oilseed - Legume,
crp.con.oilseed_maize = Oilseed - Maize,
crp.con.legume_maize = Legume - Maize,
sh.con.control_herbaceous = control - herbaceous,
sh.con.control_woody = control - woody,
sh.con.herbaceous_woody = herbaceous - woody) %>%

```

```

pivot_longer(cols = -c(.chain, .iteration, .draw),
              values_to = "coef", names_to = "par") %>%
mutate(class = case_when(
  par %in% c("Cereal", "Vegetable", "Oilseed", "Legume", "Maize") ~ "crop",
  par %in% c("control", "herbaceous", "woody") ~ "habitat",
  grepl("crp.con", par) ~ "crop.contrast",
  grepl("sh.con", par) ~ "habitat.contrast"
))
}

## Spread draws for b_Intercept and r_study (Intercept)
var_eff_tab_int <- function(mod, var) {

  if(var == "study") {
    mod %>%
      spread_draws(b_Intercept, r_study[condition, term]) %>% # draw b_Intercept and r_study
      filter(term == "Intercept") %>% # drop the slope term of r_study
      # sum b_Intercept and r_study and calculate credible intervals
      median_qi(condition_mean = b_Intercept + r_study, .width = c(0.95, 0.66)) %>%
      mutate(condition_mean = exp(condition_mean), # back-transform to response scale
             .lower = exp(.lower),
             .upper = exp(.upper))
  }

  else{
    if(var == "site") {
      mod %>%
        spread_draws(b_Intercept, `r_study:site`[condition, term]) %>% # draw b_Intercept and r_study
        filter(term == "Intercept") %>% # drop the slope term of r_study
        median_qi(condition_mean = b_Intercept + `r_study:site`, .width = c(0.95, 0.66)) %>%
        mutate(condition_mean = exp(condition_mean), # back-transform to response scale
               .lower = exp(.lower),
               .upper = exp(.upper))
    }
  }
}

## Spread draws for b_distance100 and r_study (Intercept)
var_eff_tab_slope <- function(mod, var) {

  if(var == "study"){
    mod %>%
      spread_draws(b_distance100, r_study[condition, term]) %>% # draw b_Intercept and r_study
      filter(term == "distance100") %>% # drop the slope term of r_study
      # sum b_distance100 and r_study, rescale to 10 m units, and calculate credible intervals
      median_qi(slope = (b_distance100/10) + (r_study/10), .width = c(0.95, 0.66)) %>%
      mutate(slope = exp(slope), # back-transform to response scale
             .lower = exp(.lower),
             .upper = exp(.upper))
  }

  else{
    if(var == "site") {
      mod %>%
        spread_draws(b_distance100, `r_study:site`[condition, term]) %>% # draw b_Intercept and r_study
        filter(term == "distance100") %>% # drop the slope term of r_study
        median_qi(slope = (b_distance100/10) + (`r_study:site`/10), .width = c(0.95, 0.66)) %>%
        mutate(slope = exp(slope), # back-transform to response scale and rescale to 10 m units
               .lower = exp(.lower),
               .upper = exp(.upper))
    }
  }
}
}

```

Plotting functions

```
## Plot conditional intercept by study
# I got some help with the plotting code here:
# https://discourse.mc-stan.org/t/convenience-function-for-plotting-random-group-effects/13461

var_eff_plot_int <- function(mod, x) {

  # Get inverse link function
  invlink <- mod$family$linkinv

  ggplot(x, aes(y = reorder(condition, condition_mean),
                x = condition_mean,
                xmin = .lower,
                xmax = .upper)) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = invlink( # back-transform...
    fixef(mod, probs = c(0.05, 0.95))[1, 1]), # ...grand mean estimate
    color = "#F8766D", size = 1) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = invlink( # back-transform...
    fixef(mod, probs = c(0.05, 0.95))[1, 3:4]), # ...grand mean 5 and 95% CI
    color = "#F8766D", linetype = 2) +
  geom_pointinterval() +
  labs(x = "Intercept", y = "Study") +
  theme_light() +
  theme(panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_text(hjust = 0))
}

## Plot conditional response to distance by study
var_eff_plot_slope <- function(mod, x) {

  # Get inverse link function
  invlink <- mod$family$linkinv

  ggplot(x, aes(y = reorder(condition, slope),
                x = slope,
                xmin = .lower,
                xmax = .upper)) +
  geom_pointinterval() +
  geom_vline(xintercept = invlink(
    (fixef(mod, probs = c(0.05, 0.95))[2, 1])/10),
    color = "#F8766D", size = 1) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = invlink(
    (fixef(mod, probs = c(0.05, 0.95))[2, 3:4])/10),
    color = "#F8766D", linetype = 2) +
  geom_pointinterval() +
  theme_light() +
  theme(panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_text(hjust = 0)) +
  labs(x = "Slope", y = "Study")
}
```

Model tabulation

```
model_tab <- function(mod, x1, x2, title) {
  # Tabulate slope parameter summaries
  t1 <- x1 %>%
  group_by(par, class) %>%
  median_qi(coef) %>%
  filter(class %in% c("crop", "habitat", "trapping.days")) %>%
  select(Parameter = par, Estimate = coef, lower95 = .lower, upper95 = .upper) %>%
  mutate(Parameter = case_when(
    Parameter == "log.trap.days" ~ "log.trap.days",
    Parameter == "Cereal" ~ "crop.cereal",
    Parameter == "Legume" ~ "crop.legume",
    Parameter == "Oilseed" ~ "crop.oilseed",
    Parameter == "Vegetable" ~ "crop.vegetable",
```

```

Parameter == "Maize" ~ "crop.maize",
Parameter == "control" ~ "adj.control",
Parameter == "woody" ~ "adj.woody",
Parameter == "herbaceous" ~ "adj.herb")) %>%
mutate(Group = rep("Slope", n()),
       Class = rep("Fixed", n())) %>%
arrange(Parameter)

# Tabulate intercept parameter summaries
t2 <- x2 %>%
  group_by(par, class) %>%
  median_qi(coef) %>%
  filter(class %in% c("crop", "habitat")) %>%
  select(Parameter = par, Estimate = coef, lower95 = .lower, upper95 = .upper) %>%
  mutate(Parameter = case_when(
    Parameter == "Cereal" ~ "crop.cereal",
    Parameter == "Legume" ~ "crop.legume",
    Parameter == "Oilseed" ~ "crop.oilseed",
    Parameter == "Vegetable" ~ "crop.vegetable",
    Parameter == "Maize" ~ "crop.maize",
    Parameter == "control" ~ "adj.control",
    Parameter == "woody" ~ "adj.woody",
    Parameter == "herbaceous" ~ "adj.herb")) %>%
  mutate(Group = rep("Intercept", n()),
       Class = rep("Fixed", n())) %>%
  arrange(Parameter)

# Tabulate standard deviation of study varying effect
t3 <- summary(mod)$random[[1]] %>%
  as.data.frame() %>% # convert to data frame
  rownames_to_column(var = "Parameter") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  select(Parameter, Estimate, lower95 = `l-95% CI`, upper95 = `u-95% CI`) %>%
  mutate(Parameter = case_when(
    Parameter == "sd(Intercept)" ~ "sd.intercept",
    Parameter == "sd(distance100)" ~ "sd.distance",
    Parameter == "cor(Intercept,distance100)" ~ "cor.intercept:distance"
  )) %>%
  mutate(Group = rep("Study", n()),
       Class = rep("Varying", n())) %>%
  arrange(Parameter)

# Tabulate standard deviation of study:site varying effect
t4 <- summary(mod)$random[[2]] %>%
  as.data.frame() %>% # convert to data frame
  rownames_to_column(var = "Parameter") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  select(Parameter, Estimate, lower95 = `l-95% CI`, upper95 = `u-95% CI`) %>%
  mutate(Parameter = case_when(
    Parameter == "sd(Intercept)" ~ "sd.intercept",
    Parameter == "sd(distance100)" ~ "sd.distance",
    Parameter == "cor(Intercept,distance100)" ~ "cor.intercept:distance"
  )) %>%
  mutate(Group = rep("Study:site", n()),
       Class = rep("Varying", n())) %>%
  arrange(Parameter)

# Tabulate R2
t5 <- bayes_R2(mod, probs = c(0.05, 0.95)) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>% # convert to data frame
  rownames_to_column(var = "Parameter") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  select(Parameter, Estimate, lower95 = Q5, upper95 = Q95) %>%
  mutate(Group = rep("", n()),
       Class = rep("Summary", n())) %>%
  arrange(Parameter)

```

```

# Bind into single table and convert to flextable
t.out <- bind_rows(t1, t2, t3, t4, t5) %>%
  select(Class, Group, Parameter, Estimate, lower95, upper95) %>%
  mutate(Estimate = round(Estimate, 3),
         lower95 = round(lower95, 3),
         upper95 = round(upper95, 3)) %>%
  flextable() %>%
  merge_v(j = c("Class", "Group")) %>%
  valign(j = c("Class", "Group"), valign = "top") %>%
  fontsize(size = 8) %>%
  autofit() %>%
  set_caption(
    title,
    style = "Table Caption",
    html_escape = TRUE
  )
}

```

MCMC extraction from emmeans object

```

# Marginalized across all crops and habitats
get_mcmc <- function(x, name) {

  m <- as.mcmc(x) %>% # extract MCMC chains
  map(as_tibble) %>% # convert list items to tibbles
  bind_rows() %>% # collapse list into single table
  pivot_longer(cols = everything(), names_to = "level", values_to = "slope_link100") %>%
  mutate(slope_link10 = slope_link100/10) %>% # rescale to 10-meter units
  mutate(slope_response = exp(slope_link10)) %>% # exponentiate to get back to response scale
  mutate(model= name) %>%
  select(-c(1))
}

# Marginalized by crop across habitat
get_mcmc.c <- function(x, name) {

  m <- as.mcmc(x) %>%
  map(as_tibble) %>%
  bind_rows() %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = everything(), names_to = "level", values_to = "slope_link100") %>%
  mutate(slope_link10 = slope_link100/10) %>%
  mutate(slope_response = exp(slope_link10)) %>%
  mutate(model= name, class = 'crop') %>%
  mutate(par = case_when(level %in% c("crop.pool Cereal") ~ "Cereal",
                        level %in% c("crop.pool Oilseed") ~ "Oilseed",
                        level %in% c("crop.pool Legume") ~ "Legume",
                        level %in% c("crop.pool Maize") ~ "Maize",
                        level %in% c("crop.pool Vegetable") ~ "Vegetable"))
}

# Marginalized by habitat across crop
get_mcmc.h <- function(x, name) {

  m <- as.mcmc(x) %>%
  map(as_tibble) %>%
  bind_rows() %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = everything(), names_to = "level", values_to = "slope_link100") %>%
  mutate(slope_link10 = slope_link100/10) %>%
  mutate(slope_response = exp(slope_link10)) %>%
  mutate(model= name, class = 'habitat') %>%
  mutate(par = case_when(level %in% c("snh.type control") ~ "control",
                        level %in% c("snh.type woody") ~ "woody",
                        level %in% c("snh.type herbaceous") ~ "herbaceous"))
}

```

Extract parameter estimates

Tabulate posterior draws

```
# Richness (aggregate)
brm_rich_00_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_00, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
  mutate(model = "01_brm_rich_00")

brm_rich_00_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_00) %>%
  mutate(model = "01_brm_rich_00")

brm_rich_00_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_00, "study")

brm_rich_00_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_00, "study")

brm_rich_00_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_00, "site")

brm_rich_00_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_00, "site")

# Richness (predatory)
brm_rich_11_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_11, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
  mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_11")

brm_rich_11_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_11) %>%
  mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_11")

brm_rich_11_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_11, "study")

brm_rich_11_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_11, "study")

brm_rich_11_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_11, "site")

brm_rich_11_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_11, "site")

# Richness (omnivorous)
brm_rich_12_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_12, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
  mutate(model = "03_brm_rich_12")

brm_rich_12_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_12) %>%
  mutate(model = "03_brm_rich_12")

brm_rich_12_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12, "study")

brm_rich_12_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12, "study")

brm_rich_12_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12, "site")

brm_rich_12_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12, "site")

# Richness (omnivorous, withou P. cupreus)
brm_rich_12b_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_12b, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
  mutate(model = "04_brm_rich_12b")

brm_rich_12b_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_12b) %>%
  mutate(model = "04_brm_rich_12b")

brm_rich_12b_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12b, "study")

brm_rich_12b_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12b, "study")

brm_rich_12b_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12b, "site")

brm_rich_12b_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12b, "site")
```

```

# Richness (granivorous)
brm_rich_20_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_20, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
  mutate(model = "05_brm_rich_20")

brm_rich_20_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_20) %>%
  mutate(model = "05_brm_rich_20")

brm_rich_20_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_20, "study")

brm_rich_20_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_20, "study")

brm_rich_20_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_20, "site")

brm_rich_20_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_20, "site")

# Activity density (aggregate)
brm_abund_00_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_00, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "06_brm_abund_00")

brm_abund_00_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_00) %>%
  mutate(model = "06_brm_abund_00")

brm_abund_00_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_00, "study")

brm_abund_00_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_00, "study")

brm_abund_00_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_00, "site")

brm_abund_00_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_00, "site")

# Activity density (predatory)
brm_abund_11_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_11, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "07_brm_abund_11")

brm_abund_11_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_11) %>%
  mutate(model = "07_brm_abund_11")

brm_abund_11_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_11, "study")

brm_abund_11_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_11, "study")

brm_abund_11_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_11, "site")

brm_abund_11_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_11, "site")

# Activity density (omnivorous)
brm_abund_12_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_12, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "08_brm_abund_12")

brm_abund_12_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_12) %>%
  mutate(model = "08_brm_abund_12")

brm_abund_12_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12, "study")

brm_abund_12_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12, "study")

brm_abund_12_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12, "site")

brm_abund_12_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12, "site")

# Activity density (omnivorous, without P. cupreus)
brm_abund_12b_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_12b, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "09_brm_abund_12b")

```

```

brm_abund_12b_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_12b) %>%
  mutate(model = "09_brm_abund_12b")

brm_abund_12b_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12b, "study")

brm_abund_12b_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12b, "study")

brm_abund_12b_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12b, "site")

brm_abund_12b_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12b, "site")

# Activity density (granivorous)
brm_abund_20_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_20, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "10_brm_abund_20")

brm_abund_20_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_20) %>%
  mutate(model = "10_brm_abund_20")

brm_abund_20_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_20, "study")

brm_abund_20_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_20, "study")

brm_abund_20_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_20, "site")

brm_abund_20_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_20, "site")

# Activity density (small)
brm_abund_30_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_30, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "11_brm_abund_30")

brm_abund_30_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_30) %>%
  mutate(model = "11_brm_abund_30")

brm_abund_30_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_30, "study")

brm_abund_30_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_30, "study")

brm_abund_30_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_30, "site")

brm_abund_30_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_30, "site")

# Activity density (medium)
brm_abund_40_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_40, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "12_brm_abund_40")

brm_abund_40_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_40) %>%
  mutate(model = "12_brm_abund_40")

brm_abund_40_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_40, "study")

brm_abund_40_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_40, "study")

brm_abund_40_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_40, "site")

brm_abund_40_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_40, "site")

# Activity density (large)
brm_abund_50_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_50, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
  mutate(model = "13_brm_abund_50")

brm_abund_50_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_50) %>%
  mutate(model = "13_brm_abund_50")

```

```

brm_abund_50_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_50, "study")

brm_abund_50_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_50, "study")

brm_abund_50_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_50, "site")

brm_abund_50_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_50, "site")

# Merge slope parameters
slope_parameters.rich <- bind_rows(brm_rich_00_slope_parameters,
                                  brm_rich_11_slope_parameters,
                                  brm_rich_12_slope_parameters,
                                  brm_rich_12b_slope_parameters,
                                  brm_rich_20_slope_parameters) %>%
mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11",
                                       "03_brm_rich_12", "04_brm_rich_12b",
                                       "05_brm_rich_20"))) %>%
mutate(par = tolower(par))

slope_parameters.activity <- bind_rows(brm_abund_00_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_11_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_12_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_12b_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_20_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_30_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_40_slope_parameters,
                                       brm_abund_50_slope_parameters) %>%
mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("06_brm_abund_00", "07_brm_abund_11",
                                       "08_brm_abund_12", "09_brm_abund_12b",
                                       "10_brm_abund_20", "11_brm_abund_30",
                                       "12_brm_abund_40", "13_brm_abund_50"))) %>%
mutate(par = tolower(par))

#
# slope_parameters2 <- bind_rows(brm_rich_10_slope_parameters,
#                               brm_rich_20_slope_parameters,
#                               brm_abund_00_slope_parameters,
#                               brm_abund_30_slope_parameters,
#                               brm_abund_40_slope_parameters,
#                               brm_abund_50_slope_parameters) %>%
# mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("02_brm_rich_10", "03_brm_rich_20",
#                                       "04_brm_abund_00", "07_brm_abund_30",
#                                       "08_brm_abund_40", "09_brm_abund_50"))) %>%
# mutate(par = tolower(par))
#
#
# slope_parameters2.5 <- bind_rows(brm_abund_30_slope_parameters,
#                                  brm_abund_40_slope_parameters,
#                                  brm_abund_50_slope_parameters) %>%
# mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c("07_brm_abund_30", "08_brm_abund_40",
#                                       "09_brm_abund_50"))) %>%
# mutate(par = tolower(par))
#
#####
# # Revision
#####
#
# # Richness (predatory-only)
# brm_rich_11_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_11, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
# mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_11")
#
# brm_rich_11_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_11) %>%
# mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_11")
#

```

```

# brm_rich_11_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_11, "study")
#
# brm_rich_11_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_11, "study")
#
# brm_rich_11_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_11, "site")
#
# brm_rich_11_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_11, "site")
#
# # Richness (omnivore-only)
# brm_rich_12_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_12, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
#   mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_12")
#
# brm_rich_12_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_12) %>%
#   mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_12")
#
# brm_rich_12_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12, "study")
#
# brm_rich_12_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12, "study")
#
# brm_rich_12_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12, "site")
#
# brm_rich_12_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12, "site")
#
# # Richness (omnivore-only, without Poecilus cupreus)
# brm_rich_12b_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_rich_12b, trapDays = TRUE) %>%
#   mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_12b")
#
# brm_rich_12b_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_rich_12b) %>%
#   mutate(model = "02_brm_rich_12b")
#
# brm_rich_12b_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12b, "study")
#
# brm_rich_12b_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12b, "study")
#
# brm_rich_12b_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_rich_12b, "site")
#
# brm_rich_12b_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_rich_12b, "site")
#
#
# # Activity density (predatory-only)
# brm_abund_11_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_11, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
#   mutate(model = "05_brm_abund_11")
#
# brm_abund_11_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_11) %>%
#   mutate(model = "05_brm_abund_11")
#
# brm_abund_11_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_11, "study")
#
# brm_abund_11_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_11, "study")
#
# brm_abund_11_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_11, "site")
#
# brm_abund_11_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_11, "site")
#
# # Activity density (omnivore-only)
# brm_abund_12_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_12, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
#   mutate(model = "05_brm_abund_12")
#
# brm_abund_12_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_12) %>%
#   mutate(model = "05_brm_abund_12")
#
# brm_abund_12_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12, "study")
#
# brm_abund_12_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12, "study")
#
# brm_abund_12_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12, "site")

```

```

#
# brm_abund_12_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12, "site")
#
# # Activity density (omnivore-only, without P. cupreus)
# brm_abund_12b_slope_parameters <- slope_tab(brm_abund_12b, trapDays = FALSE) %>%
#   mutate(model = "05_brm_abund_12b")
#
# brm_abund_12b_intercept_parameters <- intercept_tab(brm_abund_12b) %>%
#   mutate(model = "05_brm_abund_12b")
#
# brm_abund_12b_studyslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12b, "study")
#
# brm_abund_12b_studyint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12b, "study")
#
# brm_abund_12b_siteslope_parameters <- var_eff_tab_slope(brm_abund_12b, "site")
#
# brm_abund_12b_siteint_parameters <- var_eff_tab_int(brm_abund_12b, "site")

```

Print tabular model summaries

```

model_tab(brm_rich_00,
  brm_rich_00_slope_parameters,
  brm_rich_00_intercept_parameters,
  "Richness")

model_tab(brm_rich_11,
  brm_rich_11_slope_parameters,
  brm_rich_11_intercept_parameters,
  "Richness (predatory)")

model_tab(brm_rich_12,
  brm_rich_12_slope_parameters,
  brm_rich_12_intercept_parameters,
  "Richness (omnivorous)")

model_tab(brm_rich_12b,
  brm_rich_12b_slope_parameters,
  brm_rich_12b_intercept_parameters,
  "Richness (omnivorous, w/o P. cupreus)")

model_tab(brm_rich_20,
  brm_rich_20_slope_parameters,
  brm_rich_20_intercept_parameters,
  "Richness (granivorous)")

model_tab(brm_abund_00,
  brm_abund_00_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_00_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (total)")

model_tab(brm_abund_11,
  brm_abund_11_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_11_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (predatory)")

model_tab(brm_abund_12,
  brm_abund_12_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_12_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (predatory)")

model_tab(brm_abund_12b,
  brm_abund_12b_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_12b_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (predatory)")

model_tab(brm_abund_20,

```

```

    brm_abund_20_slope_parameters,
    brm_abund_20_intercept_parameters,
    "Activity density (granivorous)")

model_tab(brm_abund_30,
  brm_abund_30_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_30_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (small)")

model_tab(brm_abund_40,
  brm_abund_40_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_40_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (medium)")

model_tab(brm_abund_50,
  brm_abund_50_slope_parameters,
  brm_abund_50_intercept_parameters,
  "Activity density (large)")

```

Create emtrends objects

```

# Marginalized across all crops and habitats
emt_rich_00 <- emtrends(brm_rich_00,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_00d <- emtrends(brm_rich_00,
  var = "log.trap.days",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_11 <- emtrends(brm_rich_11,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_12 <- emtrends(brm_rich_12,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_12b <- emtrends(brm_rich_12b,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_20 <- emtrends(brm_rich_20,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_00 <- emtrends(brm_abund_00,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_11 <- emtrends(brm_abund_11,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_12 <- emtrends(brm_abund_12,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_12b <- emtrends(brm_abund_12b,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_20 <- emtrends(brm_abund_20,
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

```

```

emt_abund_30 <- emtrends(brm_abund_30,
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_40 <- emtrends(brm_abund_40,
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_50 <- emtrends(brm_abund_50,
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

# Marginalized by crop across habitat
emt_rich_00c <- emtrends(brm_rich_00,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_11c <- emtrends(brm_rich_11,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_12c <- emtrends(brm_rich_12,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_12bc <- emtrends(brm_rich_12b,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_20c <- emtrends(brm_rich_20,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_00c <- emtrends(brm_abund_00,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_11c <- emtrends(brm_abund_11,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_12c <- emtrends(brm_abund_12,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_12bc <- emtrends(brm_abund_12b,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_20c <- emtrends(brm_abund_20,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",
                        ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_30c <- emtrends(brm_abund_30,
                        specs = c("crop.pool"),
                        var = "distance100",

```

```

      ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_40c <- emtrends(brm_abund_40,
  specs = c("crop.pool"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_50c <- emtrends(brm_abund_50,
  specs = c("crop.pool"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

# Marginalized by habitat across crop
emt_rich_00h <- emtrends(brm_rich_00,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_11h <- emtrends(brm_rich_11,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_12h <- emtrends(brm_rich_12,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_12bh <- emtrends(brm_rich_12b,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_rich_20h <- emtrends(brm_rich_20,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_00h <- emtrends(brm_abund_00,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_11h <- emtrends(brm_abund_11,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_12h <- emtrends(brm_abund_12,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_12bh <- emtrends(brm_abund_12b,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_20h <- emtrends(brm_abund_20,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_30h <- emtrends(brm_abund_30,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",

```

```

      ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_40h <- emtrends(brm_abund_40,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

emt_abund_50h <- emtrends(brm_abund_50,
  specs = c("snh.type"),
  var = "distance100",
  ci.lvl = 0.95)

```

Extract MCMC draws from emtrends objects

```

# Marginalized across all crops and habitats

emt_rich_00.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_rich_00, "01_brm_rich_00")

emt_rich_00d.mcmc <- as.mcmc(emt_rich_00d) %>% # extract MCMC chains
  map(as_tibble) %>% # convert list items to tibbles
  bind_rows() %>% # collapse list into single table
  pivot_longer(cols = everything(), names_to = "level", values_to = "log.trap.days") %>%
  mutate(log.trap.days_response = exp(log.trap.days)) %>% # exponentiate to get back to response scale
  select(-c(1))

emt_rich_11.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_rich_11, "02_brm_rich_11")

emt_rich_12.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_rich_12, "03_brm_rich_12")

emt_rich_12b.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_rich_12b, "04_brm_rich_12b")

emt_rich_20.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_rich_20, "05_brm_rich_20")

emt_abund_00.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_00, "06_brm_abund_00")

emt_abund_11.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_11, "07_brm_abund_11")

emt_abund_12.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_12, "08_brm_abund_12")

emt_abund_12b.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_12b, "09_brm_abund_12b")

emt_abund_20.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_20, "10_brm_abund_20")

emt_abund_30.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_30, "11_brm_abund_30")

emt_abund_40.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_40, "12_brm_abund_40")

emt_abund_50.mcmc <- get_mcmc(emt_abund_50, "13_brm_abund_50")

emt_overall <- bind_rows(emt_rich_00.mcmc,
  emt_rich_11.mcmc,
  emt_rich_12.mcmc,
  emt_rich_12b.mcmc,
  emt_rich_20.mcmc,
  emt_abund_00.mcmc,
  emt_abund_11.mcmc,
  emt_abund_12.mcmc,
  emt_abund_12b.mcmc,
  emt_abund_20.mcmc,
  emt_abund_30.mcmc,
  emt_abund_40.mcmc,
  emt_abund_50.mcmc) %>%
  mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c(
    "01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11", "03_brm_rich_12", "04_brm_rich_12b",
    "05_brm_rich_20", "06_brm_abund_00", "07_brm_abund_11", "08_brm_abund_12",
    "09_brm_abund_12b", "10_brm_abund_20", "11_brm_abund_30", "12_brm_abund_40",

```

```

"13_brm_abund_50"))))

# Marginalized by crop across habitat
emt_rich_00c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_rich_00c, "01_brm_rich_00")
emt_rich_11c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_rich_11c, "02_brm_rich_11")
emt_rich_12c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_rich_12c, "03_brm_rich_12")
emt_rich_12bc.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_rich_12bc, "04_brm_rich_12b")
emt_rich_20c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_rich_20c, "05_brm_rich_20")
emt_abund_00c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_00c, "06_brm_abund_00")
emt_abund_11c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_11c, "07_brm_abund_11")
emt_abund_12c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_12c, "08_brm_abund_12")
emt_abund_12bc.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_12bc, "09_brm_abund_12b")
emt_abund_20c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_20c, "10_brm_abund_20")
emt_abund_30c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_30c, "11_brm_abund_30")
emt_abund_40c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_40c, "12_brm_abund_40")
emt_abund_50c.mcmc <- get_mcmc.c(emt_abund_50c, "13_brm_abund_50")

# Marginalized by habitat across crop
emt_rich_00h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_rich_00h, "01_brm_rich_00")
emt_rich_11h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_rich_11h, "02_brm_rich_11")
emt_rich_12h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_rich_12h, "03_brm_rich_12")
emt_rich_12bh.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_rich_12bh, "04_brm_rich_12b")
emt_rich_20h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_rich_20h, "05_brm_rich_20")
emt_abund_00h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_00h, "06_brm_abund_00")
emt_abund_11h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_11h, "07_brm_abund_11")
emt_abund_12h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_12h, "08_brm_abund_12")
emt_abund_12bh.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_12bh, "09_brm_abund_12b")
emt_abund_20h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_20h, "10_brm_abund_20")
emt_abund_30h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_30h, "11_brm_abund_30")
emt_abund_40h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_40h, "12_brm_abund_40")
emt_abund_50h.mcmc <- get_mcmc.h(emt_abund_50h, "13_brm_abund_50")

slope_parameters.emm <- bind_rows(emt_rich_00c.mcmc,
                                  emt_rich_00h.mcmc,
                                  emt_rich_11c.mcmc,
                                  emt_rich_11h.mcmc,
                                  emt_rich_12c.mcmc,

```

```

emt_rich_12h.mcmc,
emt_rich_12bc.mcmc,
emt_rich_12bh.mcmc,
emt_rich_20c.mcmc,
emt_rich_20h.mcmc,
emt_abund_00c.mcmc,
emt_abund_00h.mcmc,
emt_abund_11c.mcmc,
emt_abund_11h.mcmc,
emt_abund_12c.mcmc,
emt_abund_12h.mcmc,
emt_abund_12bc.mcmc,
emt_abund_12bh.mcmc,
emt_abund_20c.mcmc,
emt_abund_20h.mcmc,
emt_abund_30c.mcmc,
emt_abund_30h.mcmc,
emt_abund_40c.mcmc,
emt_abund_40h.mcmc,
emt_abund_50c.mcmc,
emt_abund_50h.mcmc) %>%
mutate(model = factor(model, levels = c(
  "01_brm_rich_00", "02_brm_rich_11", "03_brm_rich_12", "04_brm_rich_12b",
  "05_brm_rich_20", "06_brm_abund_00", "07_brm_abund_11", "08_brm_abund_12",
  "09_brm_abund_12b", "10_brm_abund_20", "11_brm_abund_30", "12_brm_abund_40",
  "13_brm_abund_50"))) %>%
mutate(par = tolower(par))

```

Extract probabilities that slopes are positive/negative

```

df0 <- emt_overall %>% group_by(model) %>%
  summarise(n.pos = length(model[slope_response>1]),
            n.neg = length(model[slope_response<1]),
            n.tot = length(model),
            median = median(slope_response),
            per_change = (median - 1)*100) %>%
  mutate(prop.pos = n.pos/n.tot * 100, prop.neg = n.neg/n.tot * 100)

df0.2 <- filter(emt_overall) %>%
  group_by(model) %>%
  median_qi(slope_response, .width = c(.95))

df1 <- filter(slope_parameters.emm, class %in% c("crop", "habitat")) %>%
  group_by(model, class, par) %>%
  summarise(n.pos = length(par[slope_response>1]),
            n.neg = length(par[slope_response<1]),
            n.tot = length(par),
            median = median(slope_response),
            per_change = (median - 1)*100) %>%
  mutate(prop.pos = n.pos/n.tot * 100, prop.neg = n.neg/n.tot * 100)

df2 <- filter(slope_parameters.emm, class %in% c("crop", "habitat")) %>%
  group_by(model, class, par) %>%
  median_qi(slope_response, .width = c(.95))
#
# df3 <- filter(slope_parameters2.5m, class %in% c("crop", "habitat")) %>%
#   group_by(model, class, par) %>%
#   summarise(n.pos = length(par[slope_response>1]),
#             n.neg = length(par[slope_response<1]),
#             n.tot = length(par),
#             median = median(slope_response),
#             per_change = (median - 1)*100) %>%
#   mutate(prop.pos = n.pos/n.tot * 100, prop.neg = n.neg/n.tot * 100)
#
# df4 <- filter(slope_parameters2.5m, class %in% c("crop", "habitat")) %>%
#   group_by(model, class, par) %>%

```

```
# median_qi(slope_response, .width = c(.95))
```

Plot slope parameters

```
# palette_emm <- c('01_brm_rich_00' = '#928557',
#                '02_brm_rich_11' = '#83A58C',
#                '03_brm_rich_20' = '#63BDCF',
#                '04_brm_abund_00' = '#DF8A5A',
#                '05_brm_abund_10' = '#AC4D41',
#                '06_brm_abund_20' = '#edc775',
#                '10_brm_size_00' = '#edc775')

class.labs <- c("crop type", "adjacent habitat type")
names(class.labs) <- c("crop", "habitat")

mod.labs <- c("richness\n(overall)",
             "richness\n(predatory)",
             "richness\n(omnivorous)",
             "richness\n(omnivorous w/o P. cupreus)",
             "richness\n(granivorous)",
             "activity density\n(overall)",
             "activity density\n(predatory)",
             "activity density\n(omnivorous)",
             "activity density\n(omnivorous w/o P. cupreus)",
             "activity density\n(granivorous)",
             "activity density\n(small)",
             "activity density\n(medium)",
             "activity density\n(large)")

names(mod.labs) <- c('01_brm_rich_00',
                    '02_brm_rich_11',
                    '03_brm_rich_12',
                    '04_brm_rich_12b',
                    '05_brm_rich_20',
                    '06_brm_abund_00',
                    '07_brm_abund_11',
                    '08_brm_abund_12',
                    '09_brm_abund_12b',
                    '10_brm_abund_20',
                    '11_brm_abund_30',
                    '12_brm_abund_40',
                    '13_brm_abund_50')

slope_parameters.emm$class <- as.factor(slope_parameters.emm$class)
slope_parameters.emm <- droplevels(slope_parameters.emm)

library(ggh4x)

ggplot(filter(slope_parameters.emm, class %in% c("crop", "habitat")),
       aes(slope_response, par, color = model)) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = 1, linetype = "dashed", col = "black") +
  stat_interval(aes(color_ramp = stat(level)), width=1) +
  stat_summary(data = slope_parameters.emm %>% filter(class == "crop"),
              fun="mean", geom="segment",
              mapping=aes(xend=..x.. , yend=..y.. -0.090),
              color='black') +
  stat_summary(data = slope_parameters.emm %>% filter(class == "crop"),
              fun="mean", geom="segment",
              mapping=aes(xend=..x.. , yend=..y.. +0.093),
              color='black') +
  stat_summary(data = slope_parameters.emm %>% filter(class == "habitat"),
              fun="mean", geom="segment",
              mapping=aes(xend=..x.. , yend=..y.. -0.055),
              color='black') +
  stat_summary(data = slope_parameters.emm %>% filter(class == "habitat"),
              fun="mean", geom="segment",
```

```

    mapping=aes(xend=..x.. , yend=..y.. +0.056),
    color='black') +
labs(x = "slope coefficient", y = " ", fill = "Model", color_ramp = "CI") +
facet_grid(model ~ class, scales='free', switch = "y",
    labeller = labeller(class = class.labs, model=mod.labs)) +
scale_x_continuous(position = "top") +
theme_bw(8) +
theme(panel.grid = element_blank(),
    strip.text.y.left = element_text(angle = 0),
    axis.title.x=element_text(vjust = +3),
    axis.text.y = element_text(size=8),
    legend.position = "none") +
guides(color = guide_legend(order = 1),
    color_ramp = "none") +
# scale_color_discrete(name = "Model",
#     labels = c("richness\n(overall)\n",
#               "richness\n(predatory)\n",
#               "richness\n(granivorous)\n",
#               "activity density\n(overall)\n",
#               "activity density\n(predatory)\n",
#               "activity density\n(granivorous)\n",
#               "activity density\n(small)",
#               "activity density\n(medium)",
#               "activity density\n(large)")) +
facetted_pos_scales(y = list(scale_y_discrete(limit = c("cereal", "legume",
    "maize", "oilseed",
    "vegetable"),
    labels = c("cereal\n[712 fields]",
    "legume\n[47 fields]",
    "maize\n[77 fields]",
    "oilseed\n[183 fields]",
    "vegetable\n[44 fields]")),
    scale_y_discrete(limit = c("control", "herbaceous", "woody"),
    labels = c("control\n[264 fields]",
    "herbaceous\n[498 fields]",
    "woody\n[301 fields]")))) +
coord_flip()

```



```

# Slope parameter for trap.days
# ggplot(filter(brm_rich_00_slope_parameters, class == "trapping.days"), aes(coef)) +
#   stat_halfeye() +
#   labs(x = "slope coefficient", y = NULL) +
#   theme_bw() +
#   theme(panel.grid = element_blank()) +
#   guides(color = guide_legend(order = 1),
#           color_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
#   geom_vline(xintercept = 1, linetype = "dashed", col = "black")

```

Plot contrasts

Crop

```

ggplot(filter(slope_parameters.rich, class == "crop.contrast"),
        aes(coef, par, color = model)) +
  stat_interval(aes(color_ramp = stat(level))) +
  stat_pointinterval(color = "black",
                    pch = 20,
                    size = 2,
                    .width = c(0.00001)) + # effectively removes the line and leaves the point

  theme_bw(8) +
  labs(y = "Contrast", x = "Slope coefficient difference", color_ramp = "CI") +
  theme(strip.text.x = element_blank(),
        strip.background.x = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank()) +
  guides(color = guide_legend(order = 1),
         color_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  facet_wrap(~model, scales = "free_x", ncol = 4) +
  scale_color_discrete(name = "Model",
                      labels = c("agg.",
                                "pred.",
                                "omniv.",
                                "omniv. w/o P. cupreus",
                                "granivorous")) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", col = "black") +
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev,
                  labels = rev(c("cereal - legume", "cereal - maize", "cereal - oilseed",
                                "cereal - vegetable", "legume - maize", "oilseed - legume",
                                "oilseed - maize", "vegetable - legume", "vegetable - maize",
                                "vegetable - oilseed")))
)

```



```

ggplot(filter(slope_parameters.activity, class == "crop.contrast"),
  aes(coef, par, color = model)) +
  stat_interval(aes(color_ramp = stat(level))) +
  stat_pointinterval(color = "black",
    pch = 20,
    size = 2,
    .width = c(0.00001)) + # effectively removes the line and leaves the point

  theme_bw(8) +
  labs(y = "Contrast", x = "Slope coefficient difference", color_ramp = "CI") +
  theme(strip.text.x = element_blank(),
    strip.background.x = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank()) +
  guides(color = guide_legend(order = 1),
    color_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  facet_wrap(~model, scales = "free_x", ncol = 4) +
  scale_color_discrete(name = "Model",
    labels = c("agg.",
      "pred.",
      "omniv.",
      "omniv. w/o P. cupreus",
      "granivorous",
      "small",
      "medium",
      "large")) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", col = "black") +
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev,
    labels = rev(c("cereal - legume", "cereal - maize", "cereal - oilseed",
      "cereal - vegetable", "legume - maize", "oilseed - legume",
      "oilseed - maize", "vegetable - legume", "vegetable - maize",
      "vegetable - oilseed")))
)

```


Habitat

```
ggplot(filter(slope_parameters.rich, class == "habitat.contrast"),
  aes(coef, par, color = model)) +
  stat_interval(aes(color_ramp = stat(level))) +
  stat_pointinterval(color = "black",
    pch = 20,
    size = 2,
    .width = c(0.00001)) + # effectively removes the line and leaves the point

  theme_bw(8) +
  labs(y = "Contrast", x = "Slope coefficient difference", color_ramp = "CI") +
  theme(strip.text.x = element_blank(),
    strip.background.x = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank()) +
  guides(color = guide_legend(order = 1),
    color_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  facet_wrap(~model, scales = "free_x", ncol = 4) +
  scale_color_discrete(name = "Model",
    labels = c("agg.",
      "pred.",
      "omniv.",
      "omniv. w/o P. cupreus",
      "granivorous")) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", col = "black") +
  scale_y_discrete(labels = c("control - herbaceous", "control - woody",
    "herbaceous - woody"))
```



```

ggplot(filter(slope_parameters.activity, class == "habitat.contrast"),
  aes(coef, par, color = model)) +
  stat_interval(aes(color_ramp = stat(level))) +
  stat_pointinterval(color = "black",
    pch = 20,
    size = 2,
    .width = c(0.00001)) + # effectively removes the line and leaves the point

  theme_bw(8) +
  labs(y = "Contrast", x = "Slope coefficient difference", color_ramp = "CI") +
  theme(strip.text.x = element_blank(),
    strip.background.x = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank()) +
  guides(color = guide_legend(order = 1),
    color_ramp = guide_legend(order = 2)) +
  facet_wrap(~model, scales = "free_x", ncol = 4) +
  scale_color_discrete(name = "Model",
    labels = c("agg.",
      "pred.",
      "omniv.",
      "omniv. w/o P. cupreus",
      "granivorous",
      "small",
      "medium",
      "large")) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", col = "black") +
  scale_y_discrete(labels = c("control - herbaceous", "control - woody",
    "herbaceous - woody"))

```


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